

A Study of Competency Mapping for the Software Programmer Role, in Information Technology Industry

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Abstract

Competencies are the core behavioural skills, knowledge and personal attributes that are translations of organizational capabilities and are considered essential for success. They go beyond traditional job descriptions because they focus on how the employees perform their jobs, not simply on what they are doing. While job descriptions point out specific tasks, competencies include the tangible and intangible abilities/skill the employees possess. In today's environment Competency Mapping is very important for Human Resources professional as the demand for exemplary performance will always keep rising, and they may have to develop the required competencies to keep up in the highly competitive markets. The IT industry has grown in leaps and bounds and it is has led to massive employment generation in India. This paper will aim at studying the different technical and non technical competencies required for the software programmers in Software companies and to suggest the training needs for the software programmer role. In this research, data has been collected from software programmers and their superiors or reporting bosses in various software companies. The differences between their ratings or the competency gap were studied in order to bridge the lacking competencies which would help the individual as well as the company to meet their desired goals. Finally, the study will help to prepare or improvise the training plan which will be a guide and reference to all the trainings planned and conducted in the IT industry. In the prevailing cut throat environment, developing and training the employees on the required competencies will aid in focused training, exemplary performance, individual career growth and in turn organisational growth.

Keywords: Competency, Competency Mapping, Software programmers, Information technology

Introduction

The IT industry in India is the booming industry providing employment to a vast number of people in various parts of India. Compared to other industries; IT Industry has been fuelling the growth for the last decade and it has also paved way to the economic transformation of the country and changed the outlook of our country in the worldwide economy. The existing skilled talent has been

the key motive behind India being materialized into a global outsourcing hub. India has been competitive location globally and that is the underlying reason behind the growth of the industry. Another important factor is the cost competitiveness in providing IT services in India, cost savings of 60–70 per cent over other source countries, continues to be the iron grip of its Unique Selling Proposition (USP) in the universal market. However, India is also attaining more eminence in terms of intellectual capital with various global software firms setting up their new innovation centres.

Due to these growing requirements in the IT industry, skilled and competent workforce as per the industry requirements is very vital. There is requirement for the competency mapping and competency development to aid the Human Resources professional in the IT industry to face the cut throat competition.

What is Competency?

Competency is the vital behavioral skills, knowledge and personal attributes that are translations of organizational capabilities and are deemed essential for success. They distinguish exemplary performers from adequate performers.

In that regard, competencies offer a highly descriptive means of discussing job performance. They go beyond traditional job descriptions because they focus on how employees perform their jobs, not simply on what they do. While job descriptions detail specific tasks, competencies encompass the tangible and intangible abilities employees possess. For instance, a necessary competency for a marketing professional might be the ability to perform detailed market analysis while another competency might be leadership qualities, as evidenced through the ability to build consensus.

Competency Mapping is a process of identifying the vital or core competencies required for an organization, the jobs and the functions within it. Competency mapping is an essential and very important exercise. Every well-managed organization must have well-defined job roles and inventory of competencies required to perform each role efficiently. Such list should be used for performance management, promotions, recruitment and training needs identification. The competency structure serves as the foundation for all HR applications. As a result of competency mapping, all the HR processes like recruitment, performance appraisals and training etc yield much better results.

The competency Mapping processes have to be carefully articulated since sometimes the process may be expensive or time consuming. The purpose of Competency Mapping is to fulfil the competencies gaps by identifying the training need, develop core competencies, increase the individual performance and thereby achieve the organisational goals and objectives.

Objectives of the Study

- Identify the Technical and Non Technical skills required for the software programmers in IT industry.
- Analyze the expected and possessed competency and the competency gap.

Research Methodology

Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference gap between existing and expected competencies of the software programmers in IT industry.

Sampling

Area: The sampling area for the current research would be Tamil Nadu, India.

Size: Sample size proposed for the current research – Software Programmers = 45, Superiors =20, Total 65 respondents.

Sampling technique

The sampling technique that will be used is Stratified Random Sampling.

Sampling unit

Among the various job profiles in the Information Industry, the software programmer role is one of the most significant and vast in numbers. So the sample unit chosen is the Software Programmers and their immediate superiors in the IT Industry.

Data Collection

Primary data: Primary data would be collected using the questionnaire method.

Secondary data: Secondary data would be obtained through relevant published and unpublished data from company manuals, business magazines, periodicals, journals, website etc.

Statistical Techniques

Weighted Mean Score: The desired and existing Technical and Non - technical competencies of the software Programmers are analyzed by calculating weighted mean and the formula is presented below as:

$$1. \text{Weighted Mean} = \frac{\sum xf}{\sum f}$$

Where x = score of attributes and f = frequency

2. T - Test

In order to study the difference or gap between the existing and expected competencies of the software programmers in IT industry, t-test has been applied using the SPSS Statistical tool.

Analysis & Interpretation

Table 1: Weighted Mean for the Expected Technical Competencies of Software Programmers

Weighted Mean for Expected Technical Competencies of Software Programmes		
Technical Competencies	Weighted Mean	Status
Database		
Oracle	2.65	G
MySQL	2.26	S
Microsoft SQL Server	3.00	G
IBM DB2	1.61	S
SAP Sybase	1.08	S
Microsoft Access	2.45	S
PostgreSQL	1.26	S
Ingres	1.03	S
Language		
C	2.95	G
C++	2.83	G
Java	2.58	G
Visual Basics	2.38	S
C# (C Sharp)	2.40	S
java script	2.71	G
SQL	3.34	G
Objective C	1.72	S

Eclipse	2.05	S
Net Beans IDE	1.55	S
HTML	3.14	G
XML	2.57	G
Python	1.34	S
Dotnet	1.86	S
Operating Systems		
Sun Solaris	1.37	S
Linux/Unix	2.38	S
TANDEM GUARDIAN	1.14	S
MACINTOSH	1.62	S
Windows	3.80	VG
Android OS	2.38	S
Technology		
Net framework	2.34	S
Asp.NET	2.49	G
XML	2.98	G
AJAX	2.28	S
SAP	1.20	S
Java Script	2.89	G
Jquery	2.31	S
web server	2.34	S
Active Server Pages	2.06	S
Windows Media Server	1.42	S
Embedded VB	1.43	S
Embedded VC++ (3.0, 4.0)	1.31	S
Visual Studio .Net	2.40	S
Bootstrap	1.71	S
Oracle Developer Suite	1.51	S
IBM - Cognos	1.32	S
Microsoft office	3.86	VG

Source: Primary & Computed Data Note: E =Excellent if Weighted Mean is 5.00, VG=Very Good if Weighted Mean is 4.00, G = Good if Weighted Mean is 3.00, S = Satisfactory if weighted Mean is below 2.00.

From the above table it is clear that, among the expected technical competencies, the software programmers have good knowledge in Database like Oracle and Microsoft SQL Server but they have only satisfactory knowledge in all other databases like MySQL, Microsoft SQL Server, IBM DB2SAP Sybase, Microsoft Access, Filemaker, Big Data, Postgre SQL, Informix, Ingres, Amazon Simple DB and Pega.

Among the expected competencies in Languages, the software programmers have good knowledge in C , C++,Java, Java Script, SQL, HTML and XML. In all the other languages like

Visual Basics, C# (C Sharp), Objective C, Perl, Eclipse, Net Beans IDE, Python, Mainframe, Share point and Dotnet they have satisfactory knowledge.

Among the operating systems, the Software programmers have a very good knowledge in windows and satisfactory knowledge in other Operating systems like Sun Solaris, Linux/Unix, MACINTOSH, Chrome OS, Android OS and Haiku.

From the above table, in technologies, it can be found that programmers have very good knowledge in Microsoft Office, whereas in technologies like Asp.Net, XML, Java Script they have good knowledge and in other mentioned technologies they have satisfactory knowledge.

Table 2: Weighted Mean for the Excepted Non Technical Competencies of Software Programmers

Weighted Mean for Expected Non Technical Competencies of Software Programmes		
Non -Technical Competencies	Weighted Mean	Status
Communication	4.00	VG
Continuous learning	3.97	VG
Creativity and Innovation	3.66	VG
Problem Solving	4.05	VG
Team involvement	4.09	VG
Time Management	3.83	VG
Planning Skills	3.89	VG
Priority of Task Management	3.908	VG
Analytical Skills	4.00	VG
Initiative/ motivation to work	3.89	VG
Flexibility	4.12	VG
Ability to adapt	4.15	VG
Result Orientation	3.95	VG
Leadership skills	3.89	VG
Attitude	4.09	VG
Integrity/Honesty/Ethics	4.08	VG
Critical thinking	3.95	VG
Interpersonal relationships	4.00	VG
Presentation skills	3.74	VG
Documentation	3.74	VG
Quality conscious	3.97	VG
Stress tolerance	3.68	VG

Source: Primary & Computed Data Note: E =Excellent if Weighted Mean is 5.00, VG=Very Good if Weighted Mean is 4.00, G = Good if Weighted Mean is 3.00, S = Satisfactory if weighted Mean is below 2.00.

From the above table, we can infer that as far as Non technical competencies are considered the all the programmers have very good knowledge.

Gap between the Existing and Expected Competencies

T-Test Analysis

In order to find the difference between the existing and expected competencies of the software programmers in IT industry, t' test analysis is used and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Difference between the existing and expected competencies

No.	Variables	Mean	SD	't' Test	'p' Value
1	Existing and Expected Competencies in Technical	0.297	0.365	3.545	0.002**
2	Existing and Expected Competencies in non-Technical	0.065	0.948	0.300	0.768NS

Note: ** - Sig. at 1% level; NS – Not Significant

Findings

From the above table, it is found that the null hypothesis 'there is no significant difference between existing and expected competency skills technically' is rejected. So, there is a significant difference between existing and expected competency skills.

On the other hand, the hypothesis 'there is a significant difference between existing and expected competency skills non-technically' is rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference between existing and expected competency skills.

Recommendations

By addressing the gap between the existing and expected competencies, the software programmers can equip themselves and demonstrate effective performance. The study recommends a focused training need analysis and training plan for addressing the gap in the technical competencies. The training calendar prepared from the training needs available will be a guide and reference to all the trainings planned and conducted in the IT industry and will help the trainers to improvise their current training calendar. A competency based approach or a competency based human resource plan must be incorporated into the organisation to bring out superior level performance.

Conclusion

The weighted mean scores for the expected competencies are suggesting that the non - technical or behavioural competencies are high but the difference in rating as far as the technical skill sets are considered are very low as perceived by the employees and superiors.

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